

MODELLING AND SIMULATION OF LOW-CYCLE FATIGUE BEHAVIOR

OF GLASS-MAT COMPOSITE LAMINATE

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Summary

A mathematical model involving two statistical parameters is proposed to describe the fatigue response in the low-cycle region within 200 stress cycles and evaluate the fatigue failure of the glass-mat composite laminate.

The concept of modelling is based on the schematical simplification of the experimental stress-strain diagram. The model is characterized by the secant modulus on loading and the modulus on unloading at each stress cycle.

Using this model, the computer simulation of the low-cycle fatigue (LCF) is carried out and it is shown that the model is effective in a statistical sense for predicting the LCF life of the glass-mat composite laminate comparing with the experimental P-S-N diagram.

Introduction

Numerous studies have been made widely on the fatigue behaviors of fiber reinforced plastics (FRP) since in 1964 Boller reported the research on the fatigue strength of FRP under repeated tensile loadings. Nevertheless, a lot of problems with respect to the fatigue of FRP are yet remained unsolved because of the difficulty in the fatigue tests.

Several fatigue problems have been discussed and investigated by the authors and others; the fatigue behavior of FRP under high cyclic frequencies of 6,000 - 10,000 cpm (1, 2), the acoustic fatigue strength of FRP panels (3), the temperature effects on fatigue strength of the glass-mat composite laminate (4) and the cantilever bending fatigue strength of FRP cylinders under random loadings (5).

Another fatigue problem regarding FRP which is receiving a great deal of attention is the LCF behavior of FRP under very high loadings near the ultimate strength. However, there have been few studies on LCF of FRP (6).

Recently, the authors have reported the LCF test of the glass-mat composite laminate by on-line use of a desk-top computer system (7). According to the report, it was found that the fatigue failure of the specimens under high stress levels of 75% - 90% of the static tensile strength occurs

when the ratio ϵ_r of the plastic strain to the total strain at the n-th cycle will satisfy the following relationship after the ratio increases approximately linearly with the logarithm of the repeated cycle;

$$\log N_f = A + B \epsilon_r, \quad (1)$$

where N_f is the number of cycle to failure and constants A and B are determined by applying the least square approximation method to the experimental strain responses. Moreover, it is described that the confidence intervals have to be considered based on the statistical analysis for the purpose of applying Eq. (1) to the fatigue life prediction.

In the present work, a model involving two statistical parameters is presented to account for the fatigue response and predict the fatigue failure of the glass-mat composite laminate using the above-mentioned experimental failure criterion. For the purpose of practical applications, the fatigue model should be as simple as possible. From this point of view, the concept of modelling is based on the schematical stress-strain diagram as shown in Figure 1. The model is characterized by the secant modulus α_i on loading and the modulus β_i on unloading at the i-th cycle. It can be assumed that these parameters monotonically and slowly decrease with respect to the number of load cycles.

Using this model, the computer simulation of the LCF behavior for the glass-mat composite laminate can be carried out and its algorithm can be summarized as follows; 1) to generate random numbers in a computer for two parameters so that they may follow the Weibull distributions, 2) to calculate ϵ_r increasing the number of cycles n and 3) to find the intersections of ϵ_r calculated at cycle n and the curve of the above equation with 95% confidence intervals and then the bounds of the LCF life can be determined.

Figure 1 - A model representing the stress-strain diagram under repeated stress.

Figure 2 - An example of stress-strain curve under repeated stress.

Description of the Model

The model proposed here is a simple model which is based on the empirical stress-strain curves obtained from the LCF test of the glass-mat composite laminate. An example of the stress-strain diagram is illustrated in Figure 2 which is given by monitoring the strain response during the LCF test. In order to build a model, let this empirical diagram be schematically simplified as shown in Figure 1. In this model, each point of maximum stress is connected by straight lines with the corresponding point of zero stress at every stress cycles. In the figure, e_i means the total strain and ϵ_i , the plastic strain at the i -th cycle. The area of the i -th hysteresis loop is noted by S_i .

Thus, the relations between strains e_i and ϵ_i and moduli α_i and β_i can be obtained as

$$\epsilon_i = \epsilon_{i-1} + (1/\alpha_i - 1/\beta_i) \sigma_a, \quad (2)$$

$$e_i = \epsilon_i + \sigma_a/\beta_i, \quad (3)$$

$$(i = 1, 2, \dots, n)$$

where $\alpha_i < \beta_i$. σ_a is the applied stress amplitude with zero minimum stress. Putting

$$c_i \equiv 1/\alpha_i - 1/\beta_i, \quad (4)$$

and

$$C_n \equiv \sum_{i=1}^n (1/\alpha_i - i/\beta_i) , \quad (5)$$

the strain ratio ϵ_r at the n-th cycle is given by

$$\epsilon_r = \epsilon_{n-1}/e_n = C_{n-1}/(C_n + 1/\beta_n) . \quad (6)$$

Moreover, the area of hysteresis loop relating to the energy consumed in the i-th stress cycle can be expressed by

$$s_i = (\epsilon_i - \epsilon_{i-1}) \sigma_a/2 = c_i \sigma_a^2/2 \quad (7)$$

Therefore, the area S_n associated with the total energy which will be consumed till the n-th cycle can be given by

$$S_n = C_n \sigma_a^2/2 \quad (8)$$

Judging from the experimental data, we have

$$\beta_n \approx \beta_1 \quad (9)_1$$

and

$$C_n \approx C_{n-1} . \quad (9)_2$$

Then Eq. (6) can be approximated by

$$\epsilon_r \approx C_n/(C_n + 1/\beta_1) . \quad (10)$$

On the other hand, noticing the fact that the difference c_i between $1/\alpha_i$ and $1/\beta_i$ will decrease exponentially and reduce to a certain constant b which depends on the stress level, it is assumed that

$$c_i = (a - b) e^{-(i-1)\gamma} + b \quad (11)$$

where $\gamma > 0$ and $a = C_1$. γ is a parameter relating to the rigidity reduction of the glass-mat composite laminate. Using Eq. (11), C_n can be rewritten as follows;

$$C_n = (a - b) (1 - \delta^n) / (1 - \delta) + nb . \quad (12)$$

where $\delta = e^{-\gamma}$.

In addition, it should be noted that $1/\beta_1$ in Eq. (10) and a in Eq. (11) are statistical parameters which may be considered to depend on the dispersion of specimens modulus. From the statistical analysis of experimental data on $1/\beta_1$ and a as discussed later, it is found that both of

them may be supposed to follow the two-parameter Weibull distribution.

Experimental Procedure and Results

For the purpose of easy understanding of the simulation analysis procedures, the testing method is briefly described and experimental results are also discussed.

Test Specimen

The FRP chosen for this study is the chopped strand glass mat/unsaturated polyester laminate (simply, glass-mat composite laminate). Test specimens were cut from panels fabricated by the hand lay-up method. The laminates were cured in a hot press at 60°C controlling the thickness about 3 mm and then post cured for 24 hours in an oven at 60°C. Figure 3 shows the test specimen configuration. As shown in the figure, at the center of specimen there is a large-strain gage which is put between layers at the same time when the laminate is molded. It is useful for monitoring the strain response during the fatigue test. Mechanical properties of test specimen are also listed in Table I.

Figure 3 - Fatigue test specimen.

Table I. Mechanical Properties of Test Specimen.

<u>Number of ply</u>	6
<u>Tensile modulus</u> (GPa)	13.6
<u>Tensile strength</u> (MPa)	198
<u>Glass content by volume</u> (%)	34.5

Testing Method

The LCF tension-tension test under the constant amplitude cyclic loading was conducted with an Instron type testing machine at a test frequency of about 4 or 5 cycles per minute. In the test, a desk-top computer system was on-line used connecting the testing machine to monitor and evaluate the LCF response of specimens.

Four stress levels of 75, 80, 85 and 90% of tensile strength were chosen for LCF tests. As test results, all specimens failed mostly in the region of less than 200 stress cycles which we suppose as the low cycle region.

Test Results

The stress-strain diagram under repeated stress was already shown in Figure 2. Table II lists the statistical analysis results of the LCF life of tested specimens based on the Weibull distribution. In the table, m is the shape parameter, η is the scale parameter, $E[N]$ is the mean value and CV is the coefficient of variation. This result shows that the dispersion of the LCF life is remarkably large, while that of the static tensile strength of the test specimen tested here is as small as 0.077 in CV . The values in the brackets will be explained later.

Now, it is necessary to give the experimental data on Eq. (1) since it has to be utilized as a criterion of the LCF failure in the simulation for predicting the LCF life of the glass-mat composite laminate. Figure 4 depicts the relation between the logarithm of failure cycle and the strain ratio ϵ_r . In the figure, the solid line is determined by applying the least square approximation method and referred to as Line F. On the other hand, two broken lines mean 95% confidence intervals obtained by the use of the linear regression theory under the assumption that the logarithm of failure cycles may follow the normal distribution. This assumption is easily recognized by the statistical analysis.

Table II. Statistical Analysis Results of Experimental and Predicted LCF Life Data.

Stress level (%)	Sample size	m	η	$E[N]$	CV
90	9	1.11 (1.99)	12.9 (13.8)	12 (12)	0.90 (0.53)
85	14	0.98 (1.24)	29.9 (39.6)	30 (37)	1.02 (0.81)
80	20	1.17 (1.30)	61.3 (68.0)	58 (63)	0.86 (0.78)
75	13	1.19 (1.37)	86.5 (93.9)	82 (86)	0.85 (0.74)

Predicted values are in brackets.

Figure 4 - Computational concept for predicting the failure cycle by use of the model.

Simulation Procedure and Results

Evaluation of Model Parameters

Before describing the simulation procedure, first, we have to check how the parameters or quantities involved in the foregoing discussed model will change together with the increase of stress cycle. The examples of variations of parameters $1/\alpha_i$, $1/\beta_i$, and ϵ_r calculated by using the experimental data are illustrated in Figures 5 and 6 for the different levels of 80% and 85%, respectively. Figures 7 and 8 also show the variations of the quantities s_i and its cumulative values S_i for the same test specimens as given in Figures 5 and 6. These tendencies coincide with the experimental results given by Yoshida in Reference (6).

Next, it is found by the further data analysis that the quantity c_i will decrease exponentially and reduce to a certain value b which is approximately constant for the given stress level, that is, 0.631 for the stress level of 80% and 0.594, for 85%, but values for 90 and 75% will be estimated by the computer simulation technique since only a few data on parameter b for these stress levels are available.

On the other hand, a and $1/\beta_1$, as described in the preceding section are statistical parameters relating to the scatter of specimens modulus. The statistical analysis using the experimental data presents that both of them follow the Weibull distributions as the Weibull plots of Figure 9 indicate.

Figure 5 - The variations of parameters $1/\alpha$, $1/\beta$ and ϵ_r for stress level of 85%.

Figure 6 - The variations of parameters $1/\alpha$, $1/\beta$ and ϵ_r for stress level of 80%.

Figure 7 - The variations of areas s and S for stress level of 85%.

Figure 8 - The variations of areas s and S for stress level of 80%.

Figure 9 - Weibull plots of parameters a and $1/\beta_1$.

Based on these data analysis, the following assumptions can be made in the simulation using the present model;

- 1) The change of parameter $1/\beta$ is considered to be small. Hence, we have $1/\beta_n \approx 1/\beta_1$ as given by Eq. (9)₁.
- 2) The quantity c_i will decrease exponentially and reduce to a certain constant. Therefore, it can be supposed that $C_n \approx C_{n-1}$, for large n .
- 3) Both of parameters a and $1/\beta_1$ follow the Weibull distributions.

Simulation Procedures

Under these assumptions, the computer simulation for predicting the LCF failure can be carried out by the following procedures;

- 1) Generate random numbers in a digital computer for two parameters a and $1/\beta_1$ so that they may follow the Weibull distributions, where two Weibull parameters m and η are given in Figure 9.
- 2) Calculate ϵ_r using Eq. (12) and then Eq. (10), increasing the number of cycles n . This curve is schematically drawn and referred to as Line P in Figure 4.
- 3) Find the intersections of Line P and Line F or 95% confidence intervals. They can be adopted as the bounds of the LCF failure cycle.

Simulation Results

The simulation algorithms were applied in order to investigate the validity of the present model for predicting the LCF life. Simulation results for four stress levels are plotted in Figure 10 along with the P-S-N curves obtained from the statistical analysis of experimental LCF life data provided

Figure 10 - P-S-N curves obtained from LCF test results and predicted values of LCF life.

in Table II, where $F(x)$ is the probability of failure. Results of the statistical analysis for LCF life data given by the computer simulation are also listed in the bracket of Table II. Sample sizes used in simulation are 20 equally for four stress levels. In this case, the values of parameter b for stress levels of 90 and 75% were estimated by the trial and error method and the values were 0.5 for 90% and 0.7 for 75%, respectively.

Comparing these results, it can be said that the predicted LCF life data are reasonably plotted on the P-S-N diagram. The similar comparison using Table II provides us that the dispersions of LCF life data are very large and the trends of mean values and coefficients of variation are similar excepting large discrepancy of coefficient of variation found in the case of stress level of 90%. This reason is that the number of experimental data for stress level of 90% was smaller than for three other levels, since several test specimens failed in one-half cycle as if in the static tensile test, although a lot of specimens were tried to test.

Conclusions

In this paper, a simple model has been presented which is capable of describing the low-cycle fatigue behavior of the glass-mat composite laminate under the tension-tension stress cycle. In modelling, the secant modulus on loading and the modulus on unloading were considered to represent the LCF behavior of the specimen under repeated stress. Moreover, in order to take account of the scatter of specimens modulus, two statistical parameters were involved in the model and evaluated by applying a statistical approach based on the Weibull distribution to the experimental data.

To demonstrate the validity of the model, the computer simulation was performed to predict the LCF failure under the failure criterion based on the empirical result concerning the strain responses of specimens.

As the results of statistical analysis, the reasonable agreements between the model predictions and the experimental results were obtained in the P-S-N diagram as well as the scatter of the LCF life.

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